

CHARACTERIZATION OF VALUES ADDED PROBIOTIC YOGURT ICE-CREAM

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Abstract

Health conscious people with improve health care cost has led consumer's inclination towards functional foods. Yogurt is mostly used for development of functional foods due to its good health image. Yogurt is a milk product like curd but curd is containing Lactobacillus bacterium like lactic acid bacteria but yogurt contains lactobacillus bulgaris bacterium and streptococcus thermophilus which is more healthy than curd and less fat, huge protein also, but we have to make more effective a many new food products as like one of the yogurt ice-cream this is probiotic added and which is developed most of beneficial bacteria like probiotic culture powder. Probiotic bacteria are more beneficial for gut flora in the human intestine. Probiotic yogurt is prevented digestive health, diarrhea, immune system and benefits of weight loss, mental health. I have taken probiotic powder culture for making probiotic yogurt ice-cream, Probiotic lives culture powder (contain L. casei, B. longum, L. bulgaricus, S. thermophilus, L. acidophilus) this is available in the super market. Objective: The main objective of this research was that made the best probiotic yogurt ice-cream without any change of acidity of ice-cream at home. Methodology: Sensory evaluation methods are used for Flavor, Color, Texture, Smell, and Taste of yogurt ice-cream. And Based on some important parameter of probiotic yogurt ice-cream we are analyzed the quality of probiotic yogurt ice-cream as like microbial growth, consistency, and analysis of some important nutrients like proteins, fats, carbohydrates, etc. in food analysis lab. Result: By using Hedonic Rating Scale the scoring of developed product was on the Scale of 8, positive responses of trained panelist. Aim of this study easily making the cheapest and durable, healthier functional foods a probiotic yogurt ice-cream at home.

Keywords: probiotic yogurt, gut flora, digestive health, microbial growth.

INTRODUCTION

It has been known for a long time that diet can have a positive or negative effect upon human health. In industrialized countries, a diet based on too much fat is the cause of diseases, such as hypertension and obesity. On the contrary, in developing countries, a poor diet causes serious nutritional deficiencies and death. Therefore, in recent years, there has been an increasing interest in food nutrition, with a view to safeguarding health. In fact, consumers are more aware about the link between food and health; this explains the reason for an increasing demand for foods that promote good health, such as functional foods [1].

The term functional food was used for the first time in Japan in the mid-1980s [2]. In addition to making nutrients, functional foods have a positive influence on the health of the host by helping to reduce the risk of contracting certain diseases [3].

Each area of our body is colonized by micro-organisms; most of them lie in our gut. Gut microbiota is the terminology used to describe the huge amount of microorganisms that colonize the entire digestive tract [4]. Thus, the original microbiota creates an important barrier between the external environment and the individual, avoiding a wide variety of disorders [5].

It is possible to ingest some selected bacteria, such as probiotics, which may beneficially affect the human gastrointestinal tract. The first person to realize the positive effect of selected microorganisms on human health was Eli Metchnikoff. He suggested that "the dependence of the intestinal microbes on the food makes it possible to adopt measures to modify the flora in our bodies and to replace the harmful microbes by useful microbes" [6].

Fermented dairy products are ideal food matrix for promoting probiotics and increasing their viability. An important technological property of a probiotic culture is the viability during process and storage. Factors including probiotic species, incubation level, incubation temperature, final incubation pH, the presence of hydrogen peroxide and oxygen, metabolite concentration, the presence of other microorganisms, medium lactic

and acetic acid levels and storage temperature are affective in the viability of probiotics in the food [7,8]. However, the viability of probiotics in the acidic environment vary depending on the species [9]. The relation between the viability of probiotics and the probiotic species during the storage of the products are significant [10].

There is a novel trend for using fruits, cereals and especially fruit juices with high phenolic content in probiotic yoghurt production in order to promote the development of probiotics and preserve their viability [7]. The level of using of non-dairy ingredients (fruits, vegetables, fruit juices, pulps and mashes) in yoghurt production is limited to 50% maximum (m/m). There are many studies on fruit-food matrix which have positive effects on the viability and activity of probiotics. In these studies, it was reported different fruit juice and concentrates were used in yoghurt production and some of them were affective in the preservation of the viability of probiotics [11, 12, 13].The effect of fruit juice fortification of the viability of probiotics vary depending on some factors including culture preparation method, fruit juice concentration, culture ratio, storage temperature and oxygen levels [12].

Ice cream is a palatable and highly nutritious food, prepared from the buffalo and cow milk or combination of the both, the other ingredients are cane sugar, dextrose, fruit juices, preserved fruit, nuts, chocolate, edible flavor and permitted food colors. Ice cream production is rapidly developing technology that has become a profitable industry because of recent advances. Diverse ingredients and methods of freezing have resulted in 240 different types of ice cream [25]. Many under-nourished individuals are deficient in lactase and cannot tolerate appreciable quantities of milk or milk solids. Many who suffer lactose intolerance mistakenly believe that they must avoid all dairy products. The conversion of milk to yoghurt should make it possible for these groups to consume appreciable quantities of milk with minimal symptoms of lactose intolerance due to reduction in lactose (approximately 30%) during fermentation[24]. Yoghurt is an excellent food that is easy to digest and is of high biological value and is known to lower cholesterol levels (Guyen & Kara 2002). The use of yoghurt instead of milk decreased the viscosity of ice cream mix and over-run capacity of ice cream [20].Thus aim of present study was to produce and evaluate the quality characteristics of yoghurt ice cream.

MATERIALS &METHODOLOGY

To make probiotic yogurt ice-cream at home, first developed probiotic yogurt than making probiotic yogurt icecream.

Developed Probiotic Yogurt:

Milk containing fat 6.0%, SNF 9.0%, in 100 g, energy, Kcal 86.4g, saturated fat 3.9g, carbohydrates 5.0g, protein 3.1g, calcium 108mg. was obtain from(Amul Gold, pasteurized full cream milk) local market sharda Nagar Rae Bareli road, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India. And live& Active Freezed-dried Starter probiotic powder culture (contains Casei, Bifidus& Acidophilus) was purchasing from online Ammazon.

Chart:1 flow chart of Developed Probiotic Yogurt

Developed Probiotic Yogurt Ice-cream:

Probiotic yogurt was developed at home and ice-cream powder, flavorings, butterfat, federally approved additives and Sugar was purchase in local market, sharda Nagar Rae Bareli road, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Chart 2: flow chart of Developed Probiotic Yogurt Ice-cream

pH. measurement: The pH of yogurt ice cream was measured by using a digital pH meter (InoLab pH 720 model, WTW, GmbH, Germany) (Bradley et al., 1993).

Nutrients analysis:-Total solids, protein, fat and ash contents of yoghurt ice-cream were analyzed according to methods as described by Association of Official Analytical Chemists [14].

Sensory evaluations: Sensory attributes of yoghurt ice-cream (fresh and stored) were evaluated according the scheme of Nelson and Trout [15]. The sensory panel comprising of 6 judges were selected and they were first experienced with various sensory attributes like appearance/color, flavor, body/texture and melting quality of the product i.e. (yoghurt ice-cream) and thereafter samples were served to rate the score.

Statistical analysis: The data was collected from different parts were analyzed on the software of SPSS.20 version.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Result: In the present study some preliminary trials were performed to produce yoghurt ice cream from pasteurized milk and yoghurt as a basic ingredient for the mix with ratio of 1:3, 1:1, 3:1 and 2:1, respectively. Some difficulties were experienced during initial trials. However, it was successfully produced as acceptable product from mix containing 70% milk and 30% yoghurt with addition of 15% sugar and 0.1% gelatin. Similar studies were conducted by El-Nagar et al. (2002)[16], who produced ice-cream from stirred yoghurt blended with ice-cream pre-mix (1:1) and frozen in a batch-top ice cream maker, whereas, Caisip and Resubal (2001) and Jaswinder et al. (2006) prepared yoghurt ice cream by direct inoculation of aged ice-cream mix with starter culture prior to freezing. While Guner et al. (2007) produced it from mix blended with 74.3% yoghurt [21,17,20].

Table: 1 Nutrients composition of yogurt ice- cream

Characteristic	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Total solid content (%)	30.27	37.34	33.64
Protein (%)	4.43	5.78	5.20
Fat (%)	3.87	5.30	4.74
Ash(%)	.76	2.24	1.06

Results shown in Table 1 revealed that total Solids Content (TS) of yoghurt ice-cream was in between 30.27 and 37.34% and averaged in concentration of 33.64%. The result of the present study is consistent with the findings of El-Owni and Zeinab (2009), who observed relatively the similar TS content of ice cream i.e. in between 31.82 to 33.41% [18].

Protein content of yoghurt ice cream was found to be in a range between 4.43 and 5.78% with the mean value of 5.20% (Table 1). The present findings are not in agreement with the results of Emata (2001) who reported 3.72% protein content in low fat yoghurt ice cream. Similarly, the results of present investigation are also higher than the findings of El-Owni and Zeinab (2009) who reported the range of protein content in between 2.49 and 2.69%. It is of interest to note that in the present study; the concentration of protein in yoghurt ice cream was remarkably higher than that of observed by the different researchers [18, 22].

The fat content of yoghurt ice cream was in between 3.87 and 5.30% with an average of 4.74% (Table 1). The result of present study was not in agreement with findings of Inoue (1998) who reported >8.0% fat content in ice cream type frozen yoghurt. However, it was relatively similar in fat content to that of light class (5% fat) vanilla ice cream produced by Aimee (2001)[19].

The ash content of yoghurt ice cream was observed in between 0.76 and 2.24% with an average of 1.06%. These results are not in consistent with the findings of other reported work i.e. in between 0.39 to 0.64% (El-Owni and Zeinab, 2009) [18].

Sensory evaluation:-

Yoghurt ice cream was evaluated by panel of judges for sensory attributes like appearance/color, flavor, body/texture, odour, and melting quality.

Table 2:- Sensory evaluation (score) of yoghurt ice-cream

Sensory attributes	Min.	Max.	Mean
Appearance/colour	6	8	7
Taste/flavor	7	8	7.5
Body/texture	8	9	8.5
Odour	8	9	8.5
Melting quality	6	7	6.5
Overall acceptance	7	8	7.5

The score rated was in a range of 6 to 8 (mean 7) fat appearance, for flavor 7 to 8 (mean 7.5), for texture 8 to 9 (mean 8.5), for dour 8 to 9 (mean 8.5) and for melting quality 6 to 7 (mean 6.5) and also overall acceptability was scored 7.5. It was observed that there was no remarkable effect of yoghurt on the above said sensory attributes of the final product. Similar results of sensory scores of yoghurt ice cream produced from the yoghurt at 0.7% lactic acid were observed when compared with the control group (Guner et al., 2007). In another study no "acidic-yoghurt taste" was observed in yoghurt ice cream (Caisip and Resubal, 2001). Emata (2001) given the preference to yoghurt ice cream with one hour and thirty minutes incubation period and rating scores were like moderately to like very much in terms of the flavor, aroma, color and appearance, body and texture and general acceptability (Emata 2001) [21,22].

Melting rate:- On an average, 93.19% of yoghurt ice cream samples were melted within a time of 50 min. Dogruer reported that the complete melting time of ice cream was in between 38.41 to 40.71 min.[8]. Guner reported that there was no negative effect of yoghurt on the melting characteristics of ice cream [20]. The use of yoghurt at 0.7% lactic acid exhibited a good first drop (beginning of the melting point) and melting time.

Storage quality:- The storage quality of yoghurt ice cream was evaluated as difference of sensory scores among the fresh, 1 month and 2 months stored samples. The fresh yoghurt ice cream perceived the score with average of 7, 7.5, 8.5, 8.5 and 6.5 for appearance/colour, flavor, body/ texture, and melting quality, respectively and after one month period of time, the score significantly increased to 7.5, 8, 8.5, 8.5 and 7, respectively, whereas after 2 months of the remain same as of one month there was no significant increase in the 2nd months. Similarly Jaswinder reported that yoghurt ice cream prepared by blending of yoghurt (15-60%) with ice cream mix prior to freezing and/or by direct inoculation of aged ice cream mix with yoghurt culture (2-4%) followed by incubation prior to freezing, was acceptable up to 40 days of storage at -18±3 C [17].

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of chemical characteristics particularly the fat content (~5%), the yoghurt ice cream was found to be as light ice-cream. While sensory properties discriminated the product with attractable appearance/color, palatable taste/flavor and better body/texture. Meltdown rate was moderate. Storage (up to 1 month) quality was gradually improved and perceived the better score among sensory space map.

FUTURE SCOPE

In future can be done as powder form functional probiotic foods are developed ready to serve and ready to eat in a liquid and semi-solid, solid form for good health of stomach and prevent different diseases and as energy drink also.

As medicine used developed new functional symbiotic food products and lots of modification can also be done for different patients of non-communicable disease.

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